

STUDENT'S ATTITUDES AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS ONLINE TEACHING (E -LEARNING) DURING COVID -19

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ABSTRACT

To control the spread of corona virus outbreak in India, nationwide lockdown had been started in India since 25th March 2020. All educational institutes have been closed since March 16 in west Bengal. The 2020 academic year is a period of darkness in the lives of students due to lockdown. West Bengal Education Minister urges stakeholders to consider alternative plans to complete the syllabus during the long shutdown. Therefore, many schools started resuming their sessions through e-learning portals. The researchers adopted and implemented a questionnaire where its validity and reliability for collecting data have been verified. Mean, standard deviations, and one-way ANOVA tests were conducted. The results indicate that the student's satisfaction level and attitudes towards e-learning and virtual classes are strong in general with varying degrees between items. The results did not show any significant difference at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the independent variables: student's gender, residential location, college, and GPA. However, the results imply that there is a statistically significant difference in student's satisfaction level and attitudes towards e-learning and virtual classes for the independent variable of educational level. The study concluded with few recommendations; supporting the current efforts of the university to provide all the requirements of education via e-learning and virtual classes such as suitable infrastructure and technical support.

Keywords: Undergraduate student's satisfaction, Student's attitude, E-learning, Virtual classes, COVID-19

INTRODUCTION

The impact of COVID 19, particularly on education, work opportunity, economy, and governance is immense and unprecedented worldwide (papapicco, 2020). In education, the crisis has affected students' learning environment on short notice at international scale. According to UNESCO (2020), the closure of teaching institutions are believed to be a necessary precautionary measure to influence the spread of pandemic (viner,

et. al., 2020). Closure of teaching institutions and sudden reliance on distance learning have completely erupted the normal teaching practice and led to innovative learning and teaching methods in supporting students' learning amidst the pandemic crisis. The impact on teaching and learning practices and outcomes provides a rich field for investigation and research (Iyer, Aziz, & ojcius,2020). Data on the implication of closure and learning practices could be generated from surveys and interviews related more specifically to COVID-19 impact on student learning and teaching experience. The work we present aims at evaluating the attitude and satisfaction level of undergraduate students in regard to the adopted measures of e-learning and virtual classes.

Keller and cernerud (2002) have identified variables such as age, gender, previous experience of computers, technology acceptance and individual learning styles as major predictive factors when discussing acceptance of technology by students. Usually, teachers use their smart phone for executing teaching-learning activities. It has also become affordable to students due to the reduction in the cost of both hardware and high-speed internet connection. Students wanted learning materials that are accessible through online mode in mobile phones and computers (Radha et al., 2020). But before lockdown, this technology is not to be used in our education system. The nationwide lockdown has created a scope to the school teachers to maximize the utilization of virtual platforms for the teaching-learning purposes. For maintaining the new norm of social distancing because of Covid-19, the e-learning platform has emerged as the only available way of teaching. E-learning has become quite popular among the students across the world particularly, the lockdown period due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Radha et al., 2020).

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The word 'Lockdown' has been familiarized all over the world during the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak. A fair assessment of students' perception in e-learning may grant a good precedent in the implementation of full online learning due to physical isolation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Krishnapatria, k.2020). The entire education system has become stagnant as the lockdown has been tightened to prevent the spread of the virus. In this case, educational institutions across the country had to shut down immediately, even at a time when academic sessions were held quite effectively. To minimize the lockdown effect, the teachers started taking online classes. The educational institutions took the necessary steps to continue the teaching process from home. As a result, e-learning strategies have gained momentum as well as become an important contemporary trend in education during the lockdown. To find out the impact of this online classes, the researcher aims to find out the following research questions:

1. To Measure the student's satisfaction level and attitudes of students toward e-learning and virtual classes during the COVID-19.

2. To disclose the presence of statistically significant differences in students satisfaction difference in students satisfaction level and attitudes in the e-learning and virtual classes.

METHOD

Population

The population of the current study comprised the students studying in colleges (Govt. and Govt. Aided) of West Bengal.

SAMPLE & SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

B.A / B.SC./B.COM. student of general degree college (Govt. & Govt. Aided) in different district of west Bengal has been considered as sample group for the present study. The online questionnaire through Google Forms has been prepared for collecting data. Among the student, only 175 samples are scrutinized based on the stratified sampling method. The period of study in the month of April 2020.

ANALYSIS

Willingness toward the E-learning

The revolution of information of technology has a major impact on contemporary education. It is playing a major role in all new pedagogical skills in education at all levels. Digital devices and gadgets not only provide students to engage in entertainment, but also make more opportunities for them to engage in learning activities. In this context, student's willingness toward e-learning is presented in table-1

Table-1: student's willingness towards e-learning

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	144	82.29
No	9	5.14
Maybe	22	12.57
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 82.86 percent of students have reported that their self-study skills have improved because of e-learning. Around 12.57 % of them have opined that they are somehow learning from e-sources because there are no other alternatives.

Most of the students have participated in the e-learning process in those organizations and only 5.14 % students are not able to participate in the e-learning process due to the lack of poor internet connections. It is evident from the Table-1 that a maximum number of respondents are engaged in the e-learning process.

Improvement of student's self-study skill through E-learning

Now a day learner's expectation is very different from the past. After globalization, education has integrated itself with digital technology. The nature of learning material has changed. Students want learning materials that are accessible through online mode in mobile phones and computers. The main reason for e-learning is that the students can learn at their comfort and requirement. In this context, the improvement of student's self-study skills through e-learning is presented in table-2

Table-2: E-learning improves your self-study skill

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	145	82.86
No	8	4.57
Maybe	22	12.57
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 82.86 percent of students have reported that their self-study skills have improved because of e-learning. Around 12.57 percent of them have opined in somewhat they are learning from online resources because there are no other alternatives. Since the classes and education institutions are closed during pandemic situation, they have to depend on e-learning. Even majority of the institutions are encouraging their students to learn through technology. Among all the students, only 5.14 percent were not willing to learn through technology because of lack of connectivity. It is evident from the Table-2. It has been observed that a maximum number of respondents have improved their self-study skills through e-learning.

Satisfaction level of the students on online test

Student assessment is one of the most important components of the evaluation process in our education system. Various methods have been adopted to understand the students learning capacity. The online assessment test is a prompt method which is a highly acceptable one. It is even more important during the quarantine time. Moreover, the mock test is a more effective and systematic method to extract student's abilities and understand their respective lessons, in this context, the satisfaction level of the students on online mock test is presented through table-3.

Table 3: satisfaction level of the students on the online mock test

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	128	73.14
No	18	10.29
Maybe	29	16.57
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 73.14 percent of students are satisfied with web-based mock test participation. They asserted that it is more convenient and aptitude based. Around 16.57 percent of them have opined that it may be useful since the students are pursuing online competitive examinations. Only 10.29 percent of them are certain that the web-based mock test is not sufficient as per their expectation level. It is evident from the table-3 that a maximum number of respondents is keen to participate in the mock test.

The usefulness of e-learning at quarantine Time

During this time of medical emergency, many educational institutions have tried their best to function properly. They have tried to provide students various online materials for their upcoming semester examination. Even from government level initiatives have been taken to promote e-learning and it was embraced by most of the stakeholders of education. In this context; the usefulness of the e-learning at quarantine time is presented in table-4:

Table -4: The usefulness of the e-learning at quarantine time

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	141	80.57
No	9	5.14
Maybe	25	14.29
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 80.57 percent of students have asserted that e-learning is very useful during the quarantine time. Around 14.29 percent of them have shown their positive attitude towards the usefulness of online teaching. Only 5.14 percent of them have not shown their positive attitude towards e-learning during quarantine time. It is evident from the table-4 that maximum numbers of respondents have expressed that e-learning is useful and more satisfactory.

Comparison between e-learning and traditional learning

E-learning allows educationalists to get a higher degree of coverage to communicate the message reliably for their target listeners. This ensures that all learners receive the same type of training with this learning mode. However, despite the popularity of online

education, vast groups of people intentionally stay away from such methods, mostly due to a false impression. At the same time, despite the rising popularity of online courses, traditional classroom training is the choice of the majority. Unlike online learning, the classroom learning method is more real and students have an opportunity to debate, deliberate, and discuss with their class teachers and friends. In this context, a comparison between e-learning and traditional learning on students knowledge improvement is presented in table-5.

Table-5: Comparison between e-learning and traditional learning

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	74	42.29
No	51	29.14
Maybe	50	28.57
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 42.29 percent of students have preferred highly e-learning because they are learning more advanced technical courses through online. Since soft skills are highly essential for present job market, students are keen to learn from e-learning. But at the same time, more than 28.57 percent of the students have considered that classroom learning is better than e-learning. It is evident from table-5 that maximum numbers of respondents have expressed that e-learning is useful and more satisfactory.

Face-to-face teaching is important for practical learning

In e-learning pedagogy, theoretical concepts are carried over through various application tools which make the student more convenient. But it lacks in practical teaching.

Table-6: Face-to-face teaching is important for practical learning

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	47	80
No	13	7.43
Maybe	22	12.57
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, 80 percent of students are the supporter of conventional teaching for the practical session. Around 12.57 percent of them have opted it as it may be conventional teaching is important for the practical session. And only 7.43 percent of

them are not positive on e-learning for the practical session. It is evident from table-6; a maximum number of respondent are favouring conventional teaching for practical learning.

Technical Issues of e-learning

E-learning always depends on a strong internet connection with the high band. It often become unsuccessful because of a lack of connectivity and an acute power shortage. The condition of E-learning is even worse in rural areas compared to urban due to the lack of infrastucture that online courses require, and thus fail to attend with their virtual classes. In this context , technical issues of e-learning are presented in table -7.

Table-7: Technical Issues of e-learning

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	47	26.86
No	94	53.71
Maybe	34	19.43
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 53.71 percent of students have experienced no such technical issues while learing through online mode. Around 26.86 percent of them have experienced technical issues. Nearly 19.34 percent of them expressed that sometimes it is difficult to follow the classes due to poor internet connection. Especially, video lectures from Zoom and other applications are containing a lot of technical configuration which is highly difficult to handle since the listener is new to this techonology. It is evident from the table -7; maximum number of respondents have adjusted them selves with the technological isseses of e-learning.

Positivity toward e-learning

E-learning is an innovative method to communicate with the society. It is an effective way of teaching to bring out the best among students.

Table-8: positivity towards e-learning

Classification	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	133	76
No	12	6.86
May be	30	17.14
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondent, around 76 percent of the students are in favor of e-learning. Around 17.14 percent of them have exhibited their positive attitude towards e-learning. And only 6.86 percent of the students have not shown positive towards e-learning. From the table-8, it is noted that the maximum number of respondents have positive toward e-learning.

E-Learning makes knowledge wider

E-Learning provides maximum benefits from minimum requirements. Does it work in the students to enhance their knowledge ? This is illustrated in the bellow table.

Table-9: E-learning makes knowledge wider

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	124	70.86
NO	12	8
May be	30	21.14
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, nearly 70.86 percent students have reported that e-learning makes their knowledge extensive. Nearly 21.14 respondents are in a dilemma. And only 8 percent have disagreed with the statement. From table-9, it is noted that the maximum number of the respondents states that e-learning enhances their knowldge.

Importance of web-based Teaching

The use of the internet to teach and to learn is unavoidable for both teachers and students. Online courses are becoming an important component for enhancing the students skills. Students are benefited through web-based teaching.

Table-10: Importance of web-based teaching

Classificaton	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	126	72
No	10	5.71
Maybe	39	22.29
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, 72 percent of them have understood the importance of web-based learning for their career skills. Around 22.29 percent of them have shown that it may be useful and nearly 5.71 of them donot value the importance of web-based learning. From the above table-10, it has been clearly understood that many of them know the importance of web-based learning.

Preference of learning Environment

Learning is a process of acquiring knowledge, enhancing the skills, helps in improving of their career. In this pandemic situation, there is no way of teaching in the classroom. The table -11 illustrates the students attitude toward the preference of the learning environment.

Table-11: preference of Learning Environment

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Classroom learning	136	77.71
e-learning	39	22.29
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, only 22.29 percent prefer e-learning. Nearly 77.71 percent of them prefer classroom learning. From this evidence, it is noted that most of the students prefer to classroom learning environment rather than e-learning.

E-learning bring social change in India

The contemporary education system has created a new demand by adopting new technologies in all possible fields. All the developed and developing nations have concentrated more on research and development. As a result, technology has become an essential embodiment at all level of education. A country like India is keen to introduce more new web-based courses for the students to fit them into the global job market. The present learners are highly motivated by international exposures. Technological innovations are highly influential in this society. Technology allowed us to learn many things and it provided an opportunity to utilize the technology without any discrimination. In this context, it is important to understand that e-learning brings a social change in India.

Table-12: can e-learning bring a social change in India

Classification	Respondent	Percentage
Strongly disagree	13	7.43
Disagree	7	4.00
Neutral	72	41.14
Agree	63	36.00
Strongly agree	20	11.43
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 90 percent of students have opined that e-learning is significantly playing a major role in the social change in India. They have categorically explained that e-learning can provide inclusive education. It gives learners freedom of knowledge sharing. It is evident from table-12 that the maximum number of respondents are optimistic about social change.

Types of application tools preferred to use for e-learning

Table-13: Types of device, prefer to use for e-learning

Classification	Respondent	Percentage
Laptop	53	30.29
Mobile	94	53.71
Desktop	5	2.86
Laptop & Mobile	13	7.43
Laptop & Desktop	5	2.86
Laptop, Mobile & Desktop	5	2.86
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 53.71 percent of students have preferred mobile phones for e-learning, followed by Laptop 30.29 percent, and remaining students prefer Laptop & Mobile (7.43%), Laptop, Mobile and Desktop (2.86%) respectively.

Types of application tools preferred to use for e-learning

Table-14: Types of application tools prefer to use for e-learning

Classification	Respondents	Percentage
Zoom	67	38.29
Google classroom	44	25.14
Whatsapp	18	10.29
YOU tube	41	23.43
Mail	5	2.86
Total	175	100

Among 175 respondents, around 38.29 percent of students are learning through Zoom. Nearly 25 percent of students are accessing learning materials through Google classroom and 23.43 percent are learning through YouTube. Remaining students prefer whatsapp (2.86%), and Mail (2.86%) respectively for the purpose of study.

DISCUSSION

To realize the perception of students on the subject of e-learning implementation during the time of Covid-19 Pandemic, we need to answer the following questions:

Description of Questions

1. Are you interested in e-learning?
2. Does e-learning improve your study skill?
3. Are you satisfied with Google Form mock test?
4. Does e-learning make your quarantine time a useful one?
5. Do you believe that improving knowledge through e-learning is better than traditional learning?
6. Do you think Face to face learning is important for practical teaching?
7. Did you face any issues during e-learning?
8. Are you positive towards e-learning?
9. Does e-learning make your knowledge wider?
10. Do you think web-based teaching is important for a student?
11. Which one do you prefer? Classroom learning/ e-learning
12. Can e-learning bring a social change in India?
13. The device you prefer to use for e-learning. Laptop/Mobile/Desktop
14. Which application tool do you prefer for e-learning? Zoom/ Google Classroom/ WhatsApp/ YouTube/ Mail

Overall Analysis of e-learning answers

	Yes	NO	May be
Q.1	81.66%	5.32%	13.01%
Q.2	83.43%	4.73%	11.83%
Q.3	73.96%	10.65%	15.38%
Q.4	79.88%	5.32%	14.79%
Q.5	43.19%	29.59%	27.21%

Q.6	79.88%	7.10%	13.01%
Q.7	27.21%	53.25%	19.52%
Q.8	76.33%	6.50%	17.15%
Q.9	69.82%	8.28%	21.89%
Q.10	72.19%	5.91%	21.89%

Q11. Classroom learning can be as good or even better than in-person e-learning. Research has shown that students in classroom learning [78.10%] is better than e-learning 21.89%.

Q12 .E-learning has changed the way students think about education and pursue there degrees. strongly disagree-7.10 %, Disagree-4.14%, Neutral-41.42%, Agree-35.50%, Strongly agree-11.13%.

13. Some electronic devices used for e-learning are laptop-30.17%, mobile-55.62%, Desktop-1.77%, laptop & mobile-7.10%,laptop & desktop-2.36%, laptop, mobile & desktop-2.95%.

Q14. In the covid-19 work from home scenario, most of the educational institutes have adopted online education mode. This mode is heavily dependent on e-learning Zoom 38.46%, google classroom 25.44%, whatsapp-10.65%, youtube-23.07%, Mail-2.36%.

Overall Data Analysis for E-learning

Question No	Students' Willing (in %)	Remarks
Q1	81.66	Interested
Q2	83.43	Improves self study
Q3	73.96	Satisfied with Google Form
Q4	79.88	E-learning is a useful one
Q5	43.99	Improving Knowledge
Q6	79.88	Face to face learning is important
Q7	27.21	Issues in e-learning
Q8	76.33	Positive toward e-learning
Q9	69.82	E-learning makes your knowledge wider
Q10	72.19	Web-based teaching is important for a student
Q11	78.10	Prefer classroom learning/e-learning
Q12	11.83	E-learning brings a social change

FINDINGS

- The findings of this study are based on the collection of primary data which reflects its impact on e-learning
- The findings revealed the contribution of e-learning resources or facilities for the students' performance.
- In our study, we found that there is a generally positive thought among students about e-learning. There is also a great interest and increasing use of these e-learning programmes for academic use.
- But, many of them do not want for e-learning. They only like face to face learning or traditional learning.
- In the future, this e-learning module made unavoidable options in higher education.

CONCLUSION

E-learning is gradually becoming a trend to future generation. With its increasing popularity, new generations are embracing the technology faster. Depending on its availability and comfort, many people have chosen to learn through it. enables the learner to access updated content whenever they want it to be the forthcoming trend. The online method of learning is best suited for everyone. Depending on their availability and comfort, many people have chosen to learn at a convenient time. Due to the wide set of benefits, it gives to students. The findings of the study reflect the impact of E-learning, students' interest in using E-learning resources, and their performance. In conclusion, this study have shown that E-learning has become quite popular among the students across the world, particularly at the lockdown period.

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